

Bolstering Up Smart Products Cybersecurity (Re-)Certification with Manufacturer’s Evidence

Stefano Sebastio
Collins Aerospace
Cork, Ireland
stefano.sebastio@collins.com

Sreedevi Beena
Red Alert Labs
Paris, France
sreedevi.beena@redalertlabs.com

Sara Matheu
University of Murcia
Murcia, Spain
saranieves.matheu@um.es

Roland Atoui
Red Alert Labs
Paris, France
roland.atoui@redalertlabs.com

Antonio Skarmeta
University of Murcia
Murcia, Spain
skarmeta@um.es

Abstract—The innovation brought by smart connected products is transforming many of today’s interactions tightly interconnecting physical and digital worlds. Such cyber-physical ecosystems blend data collected in the real world through sensors, with embedded processing, software, and connectivity to reaction (performed autonomously or in concert with the human) in the physical world. Recognizing the widespread adoption of digital elements in many aspects of everyday life along with a ramp up in incidents, recent regulations aim at accelerating on the adoption of good cybersecurity practices. These have the power to protect not only users of individual products but the entire ecosystem and the supply chain throughout all the stages of the lifecycle. A key aspect concerns the cybersecurity certification and how to ensure that the product remains secure once in use or it is re-certified when needed. In the following, we introduce a methodology to support a continuous (re-)certification process by means of evidence already generated by the manufacturer to ensure that product cybersecurity is maintained during operations.

Index Terms—continuous certification, product lifecycle, cybersecurity, smart connected products

I. INTRODUCTION

Leapfrogging innovation in embedded systems unleashed the pervasive adoption of smart devices that are currently so ingrained in our life that we often do not even notice them - from home appliances, to watches, lights, and thermostats just to name a few. Nowadays, by leveraging improvements in processing power and wireless network connectivity, such devices are not only smart but even connected, exponentially expanding their functionalities beyond the ones offered by a single product. These devices operates as part of a cyber-physical systems in which digital processing and data are intertwined with the physical world through sensing and/or actuation.

While connectivity and advanced computing features expands the horizon of use, on the other hand have also raised the impact caused by successful malicious incidents. Security

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breaches to such devices have been used, among others, to steal sensitive data (e.g., from doorbell [1], to medical devices [2]), hijack physical control systems (e.g., the digital building access system [3]), and create botnets to perform further attacks (e.g., with the infamous Mirai malware [4]). Omnipresence of connected smart products along with their tight operations with the physical world and the ever evolving threats are calling regulators around the globe to enhance cybersecurity by promoting new standards. Indeed, some lessons learned from the mentioned breaches are related to the need of: i) proactively remediating to vulnerability (possibly before they are actually exploited) and distributing security updates/patches; ii) providing (automatic) secure configurations for the end users; iii) performing continuous vulnerability assessment (as the threat landscape is always in evolution); iv) designing a better security governance with a higher level of collaboration among stakeholders (e.g., manufacturers, certification authorities, information sharing and operations centers); v) and rethinking the product security with a narrow trust boundary (e.g., network can not be assumed secure).

In the EU the response to the above described vision materialized with a few key regulations and directives, namely, the Network and Information Systems (NIS2) [5], the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) [6] and the Cyber Security Act (CSA) [7]. All in all, these efforts aim at introducing risk management measures and reporting, cooperating in cyber information sharing and monitoring, ensuring that cybersecurity is maintained throughout the entire lifecycle by including also obligations to be met at every stage of the value chain, and establishing an EU cybersecurity certification framework. In the following, we describe our methodology in which evidence generated by the manufacturer to securely configure the device and distribute threat mitigation are leveraged to enable and encourage a continuous (re-)certification process.

II. CERTIFYING SMART PRODUCTS

The cybersecurity certification process for smart products has been a topic of interest since some time. Recently, various schemes and regulations have emerged in order to provide a solution to this problem. Some prominent ones are the EU Cybersecurity Act, the Cyber Resilience Act, and

the European Union Cybersecurity Certification framework (EUCC) [8], [9].

The EU Cybersecurity Act (CSA) [7] aims to improve the EU cyber resilience and response by defining a cybersecurity certification framework with the idea of harmonizing the assessment methods and levels of certification assurance at the European level. The entities who are concerned are the manufacturers and suppliers, the conformity assessment bodies, and the end users or clients. For the manufacturer or suppliers, this regulation defines a set of requirements against which their Information and Communication Technology (ICT) product(s)/process(es)/service(s) must be compliant. The CSA will enable Conformity Assessment Bodies (CABs) to provide or issue harmonized European cybersecurity certificates as the regulation is focusing on harmonized assessment methods. This regulation will further enable the end users and clients to select and utilize ICT products, services and processes corresponding to their cybersecurity needs. The three assurance levels which are drawn up by this regulation are: Basic, Substantial and High. The 'Basic' level of assurance targets devices/processes or services being used in the consumer environment. This assurance level enables the manufacturer to perform a self-assessment for their Target of Evaluation (ToE) and finally issuing a declaration of conformity. The second level named 'Substantial' focuses on the median risk. In this level, the assessment is carried out by a CAB, and they issue a Certificate of Conformity in case of a successful evaluation. The last level 'High' aims at the solutions for which the risk involves an attacker with significant skills or resources, meaning the ToE is placed in a critical environment, for example. This level obliges to perform more thorough examinations (e.g., penetration tests) by a competent trusted third party. The certification of compliance is issued by a national cybersecurity certification authority, which will guarantee, in particular, the technical skills required for penetration testing. The CSA also includes in its scope the managed security services (MSS) to the products process and services. The MSS, provided to customers by specialized companies, are crucial for the prevention, detection, response, and recovery from cybersecurity incidents. They can consist of, for example, detection or response to incidents, penetration testing or security audits, or consultancy.

The EUCC which stands for European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme, is a creative framework that unifies member state certification procedures while reinforcing the EU's commitment to enhancing cybersecurity. The EUCC, derived from the SOG-IS (Senior Officials Group Information Systems Security) Common Criteria, provides a more standardized way to ICT product certification. The major aim is to improve trust and security in a quickly changing digital ecosystem by clearly defining roles, requirements, procedures and obligations [10]. The EUCC is an implementing regulation of the CSA providing information on conformity assessment bodies in charge of certifying devices, post-certification compliance and monitoring (i.e., to let manufacturers maintain their certification status), and the consequences for the identification of non-conforming products (i.e., maintaining an active stance post-certification).

The assurance levels being defined under the EUCC are Substantial and High. There are several obligations on the manufacturer for attaining the certification, which includes requirements such as to implement a proper vulnerability management system and to perform regular vulnerability analysis, patch management system, and assessments to be carried out only by certified ITSEFs (Information Technology Security Evaluation Facilities) and CBs (Certification Bodies) thus disallowing self-assessment. The purpose of the EUCC is to provide a revolutionary framework certifying information and computer technology in Europe enhancing the level of security of ICT products dedicated to security (i.e., firewalls, encryption devices, gateways etc.) as well as of any ICT product embedding a security functionality (i.e., routers, smartphones, banking cards etc.). This further improves the EU internal market by highlighting the mutual recognition aspect.

The Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) [6] is an EU regulation which aims to ensure more secure software and hardware products. More and more successful cyberattacks are targeting hardware and software products, leading to an estimated global annual cost of cybercrime of EUR 5.5 trillion by 2021 according to the EU commission. This happens often because of the lack of security in such products and also because of the lack of awareness on the manufacturer side on how to make these products secure which in turn creates a problem for the enterprises or consumers to adopt the right secure product. This regulation concerns majorly the manufacturers/importers/distributors of products (hardware/software) with digital elements (such as smart cameras, smart sensors, etc). Except for the sectors where some regulations exist already, all other market sectors are concerned under the CRA. This also covers non-embedded software. All free and open-source software falls outside the scope of this regulation. One of the major emphases of this regulation is to cover the entire lifecycle of digital products. The key aspects a manufacturer should consider includes security by design and security in the supply chain. There should be a vulnerability monitoring and reporting system being deployed. Some classifications exist on these products with digital elements such as Class I, Class II, etc. Those products which complies with the EUCC standard can automatically demonstrate adherence to the CRA requirements, offering a pathway to compliance

Approaches to Certification and Way Forward: To make a concrete example of product certification, a well-established standard for the certification of consumer Internet of Things (IoT) devices is the ETSI EN 303 645 [11]. It acts as the baseline cybersecurity requirements. The major focus is to protect the consumer IoT devices against the most common cybersecurity threats/attacks, by making them prepare to withstand potential attacks. This standard, although not promising to solve all the problems that are related to data protection/privacy challenges, focuses on the technical controls and organizational policies which could play a pivotal role in addressing the most prominent or widespread threats. Thus, it eliminates the elementary attacks on fundamental weaknesses. There are different classifications for the security requirements as laid down by the standard. They are

‘Mandatory’, ‘Recommended’, ‘Conditional’, etc. By performing a self-assessment, a manufacturer can easily identify where its device is being lagging around and can rectify to get completely compliant. A Software as a Service (SaaS) platform named CyberPass [12] has on-boarded this standard, allowing a space for the manufacturers as well as laboratories or third-party assessors (to be invited based on manufacturer’s request) to verify these requirements/rationales, and hence to provide a final verdict on to the assessment. The CyberPass platform performs an internal computation based on the responses/evidence, and finally produces a cyber-maturity score along with the final compliance report (Fig. 1).

Focusing on the ongoing transformation, despite being voluntary, the EUCC will not allow self-certification anymore. Instead, products must undergo third-party assessment by accredited bodies. Moreover, the ambitious impact set by the EUCC will touch upon several areas of certification:

- harmonization of perviously disjointed approaches;
- active stance post-certification;
- monitoring non-conformity and non-compliance;
- dynamic and proactive adaptability through vulnerability management.

Harmonization in the cybersecurity certification is something complex but yet achievable. It is proved that establishing this concept is more necessary than being beneficial. Various factors could impact on the harmonization such as, the type of product or ToE, the type of assessment, the type of intervention by the third-party assessors, the type of assurance levels, the cost, the effort, etc. The EUCC could be a stepping stone for this concept at the European level and setting a precedent that could shape the future of digital security worldwide.

Our contribution focuses on offering a methodology to support all the other areas identified in the previous itemized list. All in all, our methodology ease the process by achieving a continuous conformance to certification against an ever evolving threat landscape and embracing innovative patch management mechanisms to enhance longevity and effectiveness of certified products.

III. MANUFACTURER-GENERATED EVIDENCE

The lifecycle of a device consists of distinct phases, each playing a crucial role in maintaining cybersecurity. Even if a device is designed with security in mind, undergoes a cybersecurity certification process to ensure it meets established standards, and is securely deployed and configured, unforeseen threats and vulnerabilities may still emerge over time, potentially compromising its security.

This is where the need to collect evidence from the manufacturer becomes essential. The CRA requires organizations to maintain a proactive approach to emerging threats, making it crucial to have verifiable documentation and evidence to support the security of devices throughout their lifecycle. Additionally, the time required for certification can be reduced if detailed and up-to-date information from the manufacturer is available, allowing for a more efficient recertification process when new vulnerabilities arise.

In this context, standardized representations like Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) [13] for software composition,

Vulnerability Exploitability eXchange (VEX) [14] or Vulnerability Disclosure Report (VDR) [15] for vulnerability reports offer machine-readable formats for certain types of manufacturer-generated evidence. Similarly, the Open Security Control Assessment Language (OSCAL) [16], a set of models created by NIST, provides standardized formats on security controls, component and system description, risk assessment plans and results, enabling organizations to efficiently assess the security.

Regarding security configurations, the IETF standard Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) [17] allows manufacturers to describe a device’s expected network behavior. The MUD uses a JSON-based format to specify communication patterns and network access, helping to reduce the attack surface. A manufacturer could, for example, declare that only access to a particular cloud service, as well as connection with other manufacturers’ devices, should be permitted. When a device connects to the network, it provides a MUD URL, which points to the MUD file. The MUD manager retrieves and enforces the policies defined in the file, limiting the device’s access to only necessary resources. If the MUD file is updated, the network can dynamically enforce the new policies, ensuring that the devices maintain a secure configuration. Similarly to the MUD structure, the Threat MUD file, proposed by NIST, focuses on defining mitigation in terms of security policies. While MUD is associated to a device behavior, the threat MUD is associated to a threat, defining policies specifically designed to mitigate it. In both cases, the expressiveness of MUD and Threat MUD is limited to network behavior. To overcome these limitations, we extended both MUD and Threat MUD [18] by incorporating additional policies for channel and data protection, application layer configuration, communication limits, and even device fingerprints.

IV. AN APPROACH TO BOLSTER UP THE (RE-)CERTIFICATION

Enhancing cybersecurity requires methodologies, standardizations and regulations, and technical solutions operating in concert. In the EU project CERTIFY [19] we propose a novel methodological [20] and technological framework [21] aligned with the most recent cybersecurity regulations [22] with a viewpoint encompassing the entire lifecycle of smart connected products (such as IoT). Among the others, CERTIFY offers solutions for: i) secure enrollment, provisioning, and deployment of smart devices by means of automatic (re-)configuration; ii) enhanced open hardware security by exploiting secure-by-design principles for cryptographic key provisioning, secure storage, secure boot, and encryption; iii) boot and runtime security assessment through behavioral profiles for continuous analysis of device and network; iv) security monitoring, detection and timely reaction (e.g., update) in face of a continuously changing threat landscape; v) information sharing in a secure, privacy-preserving, and trusted fashion among all stakeholders.

Another key aspect is related to the certification of smart products and their recertification throughout the product lifecycle. The proposed methodology, described in the remainder of this section, can ease a continuous certification process by leveraging evidence (see Sec. III) the manufacturer generates

Fig. 1. Example of evaluation results generated by the CyberPass platform.

during the product design and development to enable end users to automatically get a secure configuration for their device, and later update to disseminate mitigation as new threats and vulnerabilities are discovered. In the proposed methodology manufacturer, security evaluator, certification authorities and any entities involved in cross-border cybersecurity information sharing work jointly.

The lifecycle of any smart product starts with its *design and development*. This lifecycle stage is fully led by the manufacturer. By collecting requirements, performing a threat analysis and evaluating the risks for the application domain(s), the manufacturer executes the product design, identifies and adopts the needed cybersecurity enablers and practices. These steps are pivotal to embrace the *secure by design* principles [23], [24]. As any modern development of hardware and/or software product includes the acquisition and inclusion of third parties licenses and solutions (e.g., semiconductor intellectual property block or software libraries), the manufacturer must cooperate to include in its process artifact and information from other manufacturers during the integration activities. The final step of this stage includes the installation of the cryptographic material (e.g., installing a pre-provisioned master crypto key in the Secure Element). Our approach foresees the generation of a MUD file, properly extended, to describe not only the network configuration but to additionally specify the device fingerprints and its runtime behavior. Before introducing the new product in the market, the manufacturer works with the security evaluator and the certification authority to evaluate the cybersecurity compliance and earn a product certification (e.g., the EUCC mentioned in Sec. II). Information included in the extended MUD can be leveraged during the evaluation process to validate answers provided during the assessment. For instance the presence of an access control list in the extended MUD is aligned with some of the requirements under the category of minimization of exposed attack surfaces, likewise the presence of fingerprints and runtime behavior specification will cover some requirements under the guarantee of software integrity. Once the certification is awarded the provided evidence (i.e., the extended MUD in our instantiation) is signed and tightly linked with a specific hardware and software version of a product.

At *bootstrapping* the device will load and enforce the configuration specified by the manufacturer, and certified by the authority to ensure an out-of-the-box secure configuration. The end user is thus unburdened by the need of performing manual security configurations as the enforcement of the policies in the extended MUD file will assure that the device is duly configured. This mechanism is aligned with a pivotal concept to security, namely the *security by default*

principle [25], stating that the default settings provided by the manufacturer can protect against prevalent exploitation techniques (only minimal effort may be needed) and the security complexity is in the hands and responsibility of the vendor.

If it has sufficient resources, during *operations* the device performs threat monitoring, detection, sharing and response. In any case end-user (along with other security services that may have been deployed in the domain) and manufacturer can work with other entities (e.g., information sharing and analysis centers, security operations centers, national cybersecurity centers when acting as incident and response teams) by exchanging information on threats, incidents and vulnerabilities.

The manufacturer remains in charge of generating and distributing proper mitigation in the form of software security *updates* and/or reconfiguration. The reconfiguration created as response to a threat can take the form of the threat MUD file (see Sec. III). This file will be generated by the manufacturer to describe the threat, and any needed mitigation to keep the device protected. According to the severity of the vulnerability and the adopted mitigation the device may need to be recertified to keep compliance with its original intended purpose or reasonably foreseeable use (if these can not be met the device will need to be repurposed). Manufacturer, security evaluator and certification authority will once again work together to assess the device compliance given the evolved threat landscape and the mitigation adopted by the manufacturer in the form of updates and reconfigurations. Also in this case the newly generated extended threat MUD file to reconfigure the device constitutes an evidence the manufacturer can present to accurately document the new threat(s) impacting its product and witness the performed due care. Once the compliance evaluation is completed and the product is recertified by the authority the manufacturer distributes the new software and/or configuration to the end user in such a way they will automatically keep a strong security posture.

Figure 2 pictorially represents our methodology, exemplified by the use of the extended MUD file. While in the CERTIFY project we have instantiated and evaluated it with the MUD, it is worth noting that without loss of generality another evidence or a combination of them can be fruitfully be adopted.

In the EU CERTIFY project, we experimented the integration of the extended MUD file [17] of a product into the CyberPass platform (see Listing 1), when performing an evaluation (by third-party or self-assessment). The manufacturer can use the MUD file as a support for various requirements, for instance, access control list/policies, be-

Fig. 2. The proposed methodology towards a continuous recertification throughout the product lifecycle by means of manufacturer-generated evidence. Colors discern the lifecycle stages of a product: design and development (orange), bootstrapping in the operational domain (blue) and operations and update (green).

behavioral fingerprints for the network bootstrapping or the runtime integrity attestation can be described in the extended MUD, and be used as a proof for the (partial) fulfillment of some of the certification requirements. This prototypical version of the CyberPass platform takes as input the MUD file for the product under assessment along with the answers to the certification form. At the end of the assessment, the CyberPass provides a signed MUD file (`mud-signature-certification-authority`) along with the details of the certification authority and a link to the achieved certification details (which could be publicly available, `cert-result-url`). The signature of the MUD file binds the certification of a hardware and software product version with the latest device behavior and secure configuration/mitigation made available by the manufacturer throughout the product lifecycle.

```

"systeminfo": "HighEnd CERTIFY device",
"ietf-access-control-list:acls": {
  "acl": [ ... ]
}, ...
}

```

Listing 1. Extract of the extended MUD file

All in all the proposed methodology allows to simplify the certification process by leveraging evidence the manufacturer already generates to provide a continuous secure setting for their products to end users. As the extended MUD file (or other evidence) are signed by a third party (e.g., the security evaluator), this provides guarantees to the end user that all the security measures and mitigation provided by the manufacturer have taken into account the latest discovered vulnerabilities and that the product is continuously maintaining its conformance with the certification.

```

{"ietf-mud:mud": {
  "mud-version": 1,
  "mud-url": "https://devicemanufacturer.com/device_uuid",
  "mud-signature-certification-authority": "https://cyberpass-staging.s3.amazonaws.com/uploads/01JM...f6.p7s",
  "cert-result-url": "https://app.eu.cyberpass.eu/certificaiton/RE02..",
  "last-update": "2024-12-18T21:07:00+01:00",
  "cache-validity": 48,
  "extensions": [
    "network-fingerprint",
    "monitor-mode",
    "integrity-fingerprint",
    "umu-mspl-list:mspls"],
  "network-fingerprint": "...",
  "monitor-mode": "active",
  "integrity-fingerprint": "...",
  "is-supported": true,
  "modelName": "High-End",

```

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Increasing frequency, severity and sophistication of attacks are undermining cybersecurity and privacy of smart products. To respond to such a scenario regulatory bodies are giving more and more emphasis to the role covered by the cyber-certification. In EU these efforts take the form of a few regulations namely, the EU CSA, the CRA and the EUCC implementing act. In particular, the latter aims to achieve a monumental advancement in the certification process by harmonizing currently disjointed approaches, and having a dynamic and proactive stance post-certification by performing active monitoring, vulnerability and patch management. Aligned with this dynamic and proactive stance to certification, we proposed a methodology in which artifact generated by the manufacturer during design time and later updated as the threat landscape evolves are leveraged towards a *continuous certification process*. Such an approach allows to keep bound

the certification process with the threat landscape as well as mitigation, patches, and secure configurations offered by the manufacturer. In the context of the EU project CERTIFY we exemplified this with the use of the extended MUD file (while other evidence can be alternatively adopted or combined for such a purpose as an extension) and its integration with a SaaS certification platform. As future enhancement of the SaaS certification platform, auto-completion and auto-validation of some of the certification requirements can also be performed by considering the information entered by the manufacturer in the extended MUD.

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